

HELMHOLTZ

Open Science

Helmholtz Open Science Forum

Open Science in a Changing Geopolitical Context

Report

Imprint

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Abstract

In an era of geopolitical tensions and shifting global alliances, open science seems to be standing at a crossroads. While the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" remains foundational for collaborative international research, its implementation in 2026 demands additional considerations in the context of "as open as possible, as secure as necessary".

While careful scrutiny of the boundaries of openness is essential where research could be misused to threaten security, public safety, and health, open science remains a vital catalyst - fostering the transparent exchange that accelerates research and innovation and ensures that the solutions to our most pressing challenges are developed collaboratively and for the benefit of all.

This Helmholtz Open Science Forum explored how robust open science practices and developing security measures can go hand-in-hand to strengthen strategic autonomy and create high-quality, reproducible, and trustworthy data environments.

The forum featured several presentations showcasing how collaboration can be facilitated through organizational practices or technical solutions. A plenary discussion followed, offering participants the chance to engage directly. Employees of the Helmholtz Association were invited to submit questions in advance to deepen the exchange and contribute to this important internal dialogue.

Program

Time	Agenda	Speaker
10:00	Welcome	Lea Maria Ferguson & Antonia Schrader, Helmholtz Open Science Office
10:05	Strengthening Open Science in the 21st Century	Mathijs Vleugel, Head of Helmholtz Open Science Office
10:30	As open as possible, as closed as necessary—what does that mean in light of geopolitical developments?	Melanie dos Santos Mendes, Fachbereichsleitung Nationale & Internationale Beziehungen (NIB), Forschungszentrum Jülich
11:00	PANGAEA: Open data or not, is this the question?	Frank Oliver Glöckner, Head of PANGAEA & Data at the Computing Center at AWI & Professor of Earth System Data Science at University of Bremen
11:30	Discussion	Lea Maria Ferguson & Antonia Schrader, Helmholtz Open Science Office
12:00	Closing	

Talks and Presentations

Strengthening Open Science in the 21st Century

Mathijs Vleugel, Head of Helmholtz Open Science Office

In an era of geopolitical tensions and shifting global alliances, open science seems to be standing at a crossroads. While the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" remains foundational for collaborative international research, its implementation in 2026 demands additional considerations in the context of "as open as possible, as secure as necessary". While careful scrutiny of the boundaries of openness is essential where research could be misused to threaten security, public safety, and health, open science remains a vital catalyst - fostering the transparent exchange that accelerates research and innovation and ensures that the solutions to our most pressing challenges are developed collaboratively and for the benefit of all.

As open as possible, as closed as necessary—what does that mean in light of geopolitical developments?

Melanie dos Santos Mendes, Fachbereichsleitung Nationale & Internationale Beziehungen (NIB), Forschungszentrum Jülich

International scientific cooperation is subject to unprecedented geopolitical dynamics. Technological sovereignty and leadership are essential factors in the positioning of international actors. Therefore, more than ever, research institutions must align their international cooperation with both excellence and the framework conditions of the respective geopolitical, regional, and technological context. This often presents science with a dilemma because international networking and collaboration are particular strengths of modern research. This lecture will address fundamental considerations and case studies in this context.

PANGAEA: Open data or not, is this the question?

Frank Oliver Glöckner, Head of PANGAEA & Data at the Computing Center at AWI & Professor of Earth System Data Science at University of Bremen

Open science and open data are increasingly affected by a rapidly changing geopolitical environment characterised by economic competition, technological sovereignty, and shifting international alliances. While open science aims to promote transparency, accessibility, and global collaboration, geopolitical tensions are redefining the conditions under which scientific knowledge is produced and shared. In this context, research data repositories such as PANGAEA have become essential infrastructures for maintaining international scientific

cooperation and ensuring long-term access to trusted research data. As a leading open-access repository for Earth and environmental sciences, PANGAEA supports the FAIR principles by enabling researchers worldwide to archive, discover, and reuse interoperable datasets. However, increasing restrictions e.g. in the USA on the availability of data, plus concerns of selling-out data by monopolistic Hyperscalers feeding their AI models, raise discussions on the sustainability of open scientific ecosystems. At the same time, global crises such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pandemics demonstrate the necessity of open and reliable data exchange for addressing transnational problems. This flash-talk intends to stimulate a discussion on the value of open science and open data in times of disruptive geopolitical and technological changes.

Appendix: Presentation Slides

Strengthening Open Science in the 21st Century

by Mathijs Vleugel, Head of Helmholtz Open Science Office

As open as possible, as closed as necessary—what does that mean in light of geopolitical developments?

by Melanie dos Santos Mendes, Fachbereichsleitung Nationale & Internationale Beziehungen (NIB), Forschungszentrum Jülich

PANGAEA: Open data or not, is this the question?

by Frank Oliver Glöckner, Head of PANGAEA & Data at the Computing Center at AWI & Professor of Earth System Data Science at University of Bremen

Strengthening Open Science in the 21st Century

Dr. Mathijs Vleugel

Helmholtz Association

Helmholtz Open Science Office

Helmholtz Open Science Forum, 11.06.2026

Helmholtz Open Science Office

Advancing Open Science at Helmholtz and beyond

- The Helmholtz Open Science Office
 - supports the Helmholtz Association and its research Centers in shaping the cultural change towards open science
 - promotes **dialogue** and provides impulses within the Association
 - offers **information** and support concerning all aspects of open science
 - cooperates with the centers in the **Working Group Open Science** and in joint task groups
 - represents **Helmholtz positions** on open science on a national and international level

Helmholtz Open Science Office

Focus areas 2026-2027

Open Science
Publishing

Open Science
Infrastructures

Research
Assessment

Monitoring,
Impact, and
Transfer

How Open Science became possible

Infrastructure (the ability to do open science)

→ *the technical and organizational conditions that make openness feasible.*

- Digitization made publications, data, and methods shareable
- Internet and digital communication lowered barriers to dissemination
- Networked and global research enabled broader and faster collaboration

nfdi

eosc

Findable

Accessible

Interoperable

Reusable

arXiv

How Open Science became possible - and expected

Expectations (the motivation and legitimacy to do open science)

→ *norms about how research should be conducted and who should benefit.*

- Science: transparency, reproducibility, faster knowledge exchange
- Society: public access to publicly funded research, accountability, participation
- Economy: maximizing the economic value of research

*Universal Declaration of Human Rights
(1948) Article 27:*

“Everyone has the right to participate in cultural life, enjoy the arts, and share in scientific advancement and its benefits.”

**Guidelines for Safeguarding
Good Research Practice**

Code of Conduct

Open Science at Helmholtz

- 2003 - Helmholtz signs the „*Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities*“

Helmholtz Open Access quote

re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

The Helmholtz Centers contribute to 91 data infrastructures (status 06/2026)

Science has never been more global than it is today

MOSAIC-Expedition, Polarstern/AWI, Esther Horvath

GARS O'Higgins (German Antarctic Receiving Station), DLR

GRACE-Zwillingsatelliten (NASA)

HELMHOLTZ

SPITZENFORSCHUNG FÜR
GROSSE HERAUSFORDERUNGEN

The conditions for science are changing

- Science has become more **inter-dependent** (*international collaboration and digital dependencies*)
- Science has become more **politically contested** (*funding cuts and attacks on public knowledge*)
- Science has become more **strategically relevant** (*security concerns and competition*)

Google

NCBI

ELSEVIER

Proposed 2026 Budget Cuts

Global developments

How do they challenge our ability to do Open Science?

- Dependence on concentrated infrastructures creates risks for reliable access
- Scientific databases, repositories, and services may become unavailable or no longer maintained
- Pipelines for data processing and quality assurance may break down

i Notice

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An official website of the United States government [Here's how you know](#)

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CAREER NEWS | 02 October 2025

Model organism databases face budget cuts and closures

Beyond the crucial data they contain, these digital archives have provided an important space for academic communities to exchange ideas and resources.

NEWS CAREERS COMMENTARY JOURNALS ▾ **Science**

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HOME > NEWS > SCIENCEINSIDER > TRUMP ADMINISTRATION MOVES TO BREAK UP LEADING U.S. CLIMATE AND WEATHER CENTER

SCIENCEINSIDER | SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY

Trump administration moves to break up leading U.S. climate and weather center

White House budget director calls the National Center for Atmospheric Research a source of "climate alarmism"

Global developments

How do they challenge our expectations to do Open Science?

- Some research outputs, datasets, technologies, or methods can be misused in ways that harm security, society, critical infrastructure, or economic resilience.
- What should not be openly shared, or needs protection?
“as open as possible, as secure as necessary”
- Uncertainty creates risk-averse approaches

What does research security mean?

Research and knowledge security is the anticipation and management of risks such as the unwanted leaking of knowledge and technology, illegal interference and the improper use of research results.

BMFTR

How do we enable collaborative and open science
in the 21st century?

Open Science in the 21st century

Why still care about openness?

- Global societal challenges require international scientific collaboration and data sharing
- Shared knowledge benefits society, policymaking, and innovation and avoids duplication of research efforts
- Especially in times of increasing international tensions, Open Science helps ensure that scientific quality is maintained
- Transparency strengthens public trust in science and evidence-based policymaking

Helmholtz' commitment to Open Science

“as open as possible and as closed as necessary”

Research designs, methods, results, software, and data are published responsibly and made as openly available as possible

Intelligent openness:

- data protection (GDPR/DSGVO)
- commercial objectives
- security considerations

In such cases, at a minimum the associated metadata are made available, and the reasons for non-publication are stated explicitly.

The need for restrictions may change over time.

How can we keep science as open as possible?

Knowledge security = risk governance

Not “open vs. closed,” but responsible openness

- **Integrity**: Research integrity is not only about fraud and reproducibility, but also about responsible handling of sensitive information
- **Awareness**: Researchers need practical understanding of dual-use risks, export controls, and ethical decision-making in data sharing.
- **Technological solutions**: Sensitive data can be shared and analyzed in controlled technical environments
- **Governance**: Universities and research organizations need clear governance structures, guidance, and support systems

How can we keep science as open as possible?

Digital sovereignty = dependency governance

Moving from over-reliance to smart redundancies

- **Map dependencies:** Identify critical dependencies in data, infrastructure, and platforms to reduce systemic risk and lock-in
- **Ensure continuity:** Secure access through data rescue, preservation, and distributed backups of at-risk research outputs
- **Build resilience:** Invest in community-owned, federated infrastructures that enable resilience and global connectivity
- **Diversify & connect:** Strengthen independent capacity and support diverse providers and trusted cross-border collaboration

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Thank you!

open-science@helmholtz.de

<https://os.helmholtz.de>

[Open Science Newsletter](#)

[LinkedIn](#)

Publications and recommended readings: [Zotero](#)

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<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.de>

AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

How can we strike the right balance knowledge security with the principles of open science/open data?

June 11th 2026 | Dr. Melanie dos Santos Mendes, National & International Relations, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH

OUTLINE FOR TODAY

- ❖ Setting at Forschungszentrum Jülich
- ❖ Why do we talk about knowledge security?
- ❖ What does knowledge security comprise?
- ❖ Discussion: What does this mean for Open Science?

> JÜLICH AT A GLANCE

1956

Foundation

1,7

Square kilometres

Campus

15

Institutes

1,935

Publications with partners
more than 90 countries

(as of 31.12.2024)

> OUR APPROACH

„The world is our perspective“

- Interdisciplinary research leveraging advanced AI, data analysis, and unique research infrastructures
- From fundamental principles to real-world applications
- Strong national and international collaborations with science, industry, and society
- Fostering the transfer and accessibility of research outcomes

> JÜLICH AT A GLANCE

18

Branch offices in
Germany and abroad

7,400+

People from
114 Nations

1,923

Visiting scientists from 73
countries

**> WHY DO WE TALK ABOUT
KNOWLEDGE SECURITY?**

> SCIENCE. IN A DYNAMIC GEOPOLITICAL SETTING.

> PRINCIPLES

Key points from the Science Council's paper “Science and security in times of global political upheaval”

> MEANING OF SECURITY-RELATED RESEARCH

Not only military research

... but also the entire field of research that contributes to the security and resilience of society.

Risks-Protection

Relevance of scientific examination of risks, threats and protective measures for internal and external security

New Technologies

Development of new technologies, methods, procedures and services

Various research fields

Accordingly, security-related research is present in various disciplines and research fields in different forms

EXPECTED EFFECT – ENABLING CULTURE

Scientist

- Appropriate framework for action
- Enabling cooperation even under difficult conditions
- Safeguarding interests through adequate cooperation conditions
- Recommendation as a reliable cooperation partner.

Forschungszentrum Jülich

- Best possible international networking
- Safeguarding the interests of the FZJ and the science location
- Regional competence development
- Safeguarding the confidentiality of our own research and the Open Science principles

Helmholtz

- Best practice legal compliance & opportunity/risk assessment
- Best practice and systematic exchange on the topic of information security
- Development and transfer of regional knowledge

➤ **WHAT DOES KNOWLEDGE
SECURITY COMPRISE?**

> KNOWLEDGE SECURITY

Knowledge security as a value aims both a) to safeguard certain national interests and values and b) to continue to protect the core of international scientific work, i.e. working under conditions of guaranteed scientific freedom.

> EMBEDDING KNOWLEDGE SECURITY

Overall objective/ Focus area

Strategic priorities: Where do we need to stay ahead of the curve?

Defining Strategic Milestones

- Scope of the internat. Cooperation
- Ensuring technological sovereignty
- Resilience & Industrial Competitiveness

Opportunities and unique characteristics of the foreign research system and market

- Compulsory Collaboration & Innovation Advantage
- Best-Practice Transfer & System Adaptation
- Specific Innovation Framework in the partner country
- Interest-Driven Ecosystem Utilization

Risks Associated with Unsuitable Terms of Cooperation

IP Security & Strategic Compliance

- IP Audit: Evaluating protection strength
- Risk Mitigation: Preventing unauthorized knowledge drain

Strategic upside via tailored collaboration

Summary Assessment:
Potential and Interest-Based,
Risk-Minimized Collaboration

> KNOWLEDGE SECURITY: A VITAL PRECONDITION

Country-agnostic "Need-to-Know" Enforcement

Physical Security

- Access and Enrollment Protocols
- Entry Point Controls
- Building Perimeter Security
- Laboratory & Office Access

Digital Security

- Access Management
- Secure Data Exchange
- Data Governance & Sharing
- Confidentiality Protocols

Contractual/Legal Framework

- Contract Structures
- Legal Enforcement Options
- Safeguarding Interests
- Stakeholder Assessment

> SUMMARY – KNOWLEDGE AS A CORE MISSION/VALUE

Strategic Framework

Geopolitical Assessment

Integrating political conditions into all FZJ processes

Scientific Cooperation

Focus on interests, values, and specific core issues

Diversification

Building resilient and broadly based networks

Support & Security

Enabling Culture

Active support for institutes through risk management

Compliance

Ensuring legal compliance in all collaborations

Resilience

Securing infrastructure and management structures.

Key Message

(The Bottom Line)

Positioning

FZJ as a reliable partner in an unstable world.

> FOR DISCUSSION: IT IS ALL ABOUT COOPERATION VS. COMPETITION

**> DISCUSSION: WHAT DOES THIS
MEAN FOR OPEN SCIENCE?**

> A CLOUD OF QUESTIONS

How can we strike a balance between technological sovereignty and global competitiveness, as well as open science principles

What are your specific experiences

In your view, what impact do efforts in the area of knowledge/research security have on open science principles, and how so

Should we adopt a form of data diplomacy

Some more.....

PANGAEA[®]
Data Publisher for Earth &
Environmental Science •

PANGAEA: Open data or not, is this the question? Open Science in a Changing Geopolitical Context

Frank Oliver Glöckner
11.06.2026

PANGAEA Vision & Mission

PANGAEA - the globally leading platform for FAIR data management, data curation, and data publication, in earth, environmental and biodiversity science.

PANGAEA empowers researchers, communities, and organizations through cutting-edge data publication, data products, data dissemination, technology and active collaboration.

PANGAEA - History & Milestones

- ▶ 1987: Core repository database – file-based data system SEDAT, later SEDAN – Sediment Data Analysis
- ▶ 1994: Foundation as Information System for long-term archiving and publication of data from earth & environmental science
- ▶ 1997: Renamed - **PANGAEA** - PaleoNetwork for Geological and Environmental Data
- ▶ 1997: First data management project
- ▶ 1998: www.pangaea.de - PANGAEA - Network for Geoscientific and Environmental Data
- ▶ 2001: Accreditation by the „International Council for Science“ (ICSU) as „Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science“ (ICSU WDS **World Data Center**)
- ▶ 2007: Accredited by the „World Meteorological Organisation“ (WMO) as „**World Radiation Monitoring Center**“ (WRMC)
- ▶ 2009: DataCite founded, citation of datasets in PANGAEA via unique **DOIs** established
- ▶ 2010: **Renamed - PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science**
- ▶ 2011: Ticket system established
- ▶ 2019: **Certified by Core Trust Seal**
- ▶ 2024: PANGAEA as a resilient **platform** with front-offices

FAIR Data Archiving & Publication: PANGAEA

Datasets: > 445,000
Data items: > 36 billion
Projects: 960

June 2026

FAIR Dissemination of (Meta-)Data

Open Science

Helmholtz: On the Way to Openness by Design

In line with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science¹ and the enshrining of open science in national, European, and international science policy, Helmholtz commits itself to open science.

Science lives on the open exchange of knowledge. Sharing, networking, and collaborating are central elements of the culture of scientific endeavour. Digitalization dynamically advances the possibilities of this culture. The paradigm of openness thus opens up new prospects in the entire scientific research cycle and enables research results to be made openly accessible and broadly reusable in sustainable infrastructures. This open culture of scientific endeavour is captured by the term “open science,” and is a guiding principle for Helmholtz in keeping with good scientific practice.

All Centers will establish detailed procedures for managing research data in publicly available policies,⁶ and will regularly examine and if necessary, adapt these procedures.

September 2022 <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/open-science-in-helmholtz/open-science-policy/>

DFG Guideline 13: Providing public access to research results

As a rule, researchers make all results available as part of scientific/academic discourse.

In specific cases, however, there may be reasons not to make results publicly available (in the narrower sense of publication, but also in a broader sense through other communication channels); this decision must not depend on third parties. Researchers decide autonomously – with due regard for the conventions of the relevant subject area – whether, how and where to disseminate their results.

If it has been decided to make results available in the public domain, researchers describe them clearly and in full.

Where possible and reasonable, this includes making the research data, materials and information on which the results are based, as well as the methods and software used, available and fully explaining the work processes.

September 2019, last update January 2025
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281892>

Open Science

Kultur der Datennutzung und des Datenteilens

Wir wollen eine Kultur der Datennutzung und des Datenteilens, die Datenökonomie etabliert, auf Innovation setzt und Grund- und Freiheitsrechte schützt. Dafür beseitigen wir Rechts-unsicherheiten, heben Datenschätze, fördern Daten-Ökosysteme und setzen auf Datensouveränität. Wir schaffen die Grundlage, um Regelwerke, für die es sachgemäß ist, in einem Datengesetzbuch zusammenzufassen.

Wir verfolgen den Grundsatz „public money, public data“ und gewährleisten dabei durch Datentreuhänder Vertrauen in Datenmanagement und hohe Datenqualität.

Wo es möglich ist, schaffen wir einen Rechtsanspruch auf Open Data bei staatlichen Einrichtungen. Wir schaffen eine moderne Regelung für Mobilitäts-, Gesundheits- und Forschungsdaten. Dabei wahren wir alle berechtigten Interessen.

CDU, CSU, SPD (2025) – Verantwortung für Deutschland, <https://www.koalitionsvertrag2025.de/>

Joint Statement on Open Science: *Open Science as a pillar for strengthening the European Research Area Opportunities and remaining barriers*

Open Science is fundamental to the 'fifth freedom' - the free circulation of knowledge. The research and education system is being strengthened by Member States' support and incentive structures that advance the uptake of Open Science and Open Education (OE) practices, including opening methods, protocols, software, and outputs such as articles, books, preprints, and research data. In line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, this enhances reproducibility, transparency, and trustworthiness, strengthens evidence-based policymaking and democracy, and supports competitiveness.

1. Equitable and sustainable access to Open Access and other research outputs
2. Rights, legal clarity, and harmonisation
3. **Research data, FAIR, and capacity**
4. Open Science for innovation, security, and AI
5. Inclusiveness, multilingualism, and societal engagement
6. Open, federated, and sovereign infrastructures
7. Incentives and research assessment

3. Research data, FAIR, and capacity

Gaps persist in the accessibility and reuse of research data, with inconsistent FAIR implementation and insufficient metadata and repositories.

Research information should be made open and reusable with appropriate safeguards, ensuring transparency, resilience, and independence. There is a need to:

- Strengthen FAIR data practices, building on a better understanding of current gaps.
- Improve the discoverability and interoperability of research data by developing key national infrastructures and preserving key data, also to help further develop a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
- Build institutional capacity, including data stewardship and legal expertise.

A coordinated approach is required to enable effective data reuse across Europe.

May 2026: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20165184>

Constrained (staged) Openness

RFII: Für eine reflektierte Offenheit in der Wissenschaft

Architekturen für eine **gestufte Offenheit** sollten auf geopolitische, ökonomische und technologische Herausforderungen reagieren können. So stehen die außenpolitische Forderung nach Risikominimierung bezüglich ungewollter Datenabflüsse in der Zusammenarbeit, zum Beispiel mit bestimmten Ländern, sowie die innenpolitische Forderung einer „neuen Offenheit“ gegenüber militärischer beziehungsweise auf militärische Zwecke beziehbarer Forschung – die wiederum mit Fragen der (Daten-)Sicherheit und Geheimhaltung verbunden ist – im Raum.

Diese geopolitischen Herausforderungen sollten immer mitbedacht werden, wenn wissenschaftliche Einrichtungen Open-Science-Richtlinien formulieren und die Veröffentlichung von Forschungsdaten gefordert wird.

Der drohende, beziehungsweise sich bereits vollziehende Verlust digitaler Souveränität, insbesondere durch marktbeherrschende Anbieter von Diensten und Produkten, ist auf verschiedenen Ebenen ausführlich und zutreffend diagnostiziert worden.

Die mit generativer KI entstandenen Markt- und Machtverhältnisse berühren ungeklärte Urheberrechtsfragen, die nicht nur „Wissen“, sondern auch die Autorennennung, die Integrität von publiziertem geistigem Eigentum sowie den Sprach- und Denkstil von in der Wissenschaft tätigen und publizierenden Personen betreffen.

Helmholtz Open Science Office:

The actual tension is therefore less about balancing “Open Science vs. Research Security” but rather concerns **“Collaboration vs. Research Security”**.

We must, however, not forget that the solutions to the great challenges of our time can only be realized through global collaboration.

The greater danger to open science lies in becoming overly cautious (i.e., qualifying outputs as security risks without proper justification) and thereby withholding valuable contributions from the scientific community and society.

To avoid this, research institutions are expected to put in place the appropriate mechanisms to **carefully weigh security concerns when establishing collaborations, so that principles of openness and integrity can be upheld.**

Helmholtz Open Science Office (2024). The Perceived Tension between Open Science and Research Security. <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/research-assessment/responsible-research/tension-open-science-research-security-commentary/>

RFII (2025). Leistung in Verantwortung - Zur Zukunft der wissenschaftlichen Informationsinfrastrukturen in Deutschland. <https://d-nb.info/1375547445/34>

In Summary:
The papers are strong on diagnosis but lack – practical - measures and solutions.

Open Data or Not?

▶ Open

- Taxpayer's money – taxpayer's data
- Data is a global heritage, everyone should profit
- Civic participation
- Transparency and reproducibility
- Faster innovation without barriers
- One rule – less bureaucracy

▶ Closed (constrained)

- Privacy & sensible data
- Reduce misuse, misinterpretation
- Exclusivity: Unequal access to benefits
- Who makes the rules to give access?
- Who enforces them?
- Reduced redundancy - single point of failure

“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”

Trumps „War“ on Science

ChatGPT: "Science Under Threat in Trump's America"

U.S. Federal Science Expertise

- The federal workforce decreased by nearly **95,000** across science-focused agencies, accounting for **39.8%** of the government-wide workforce change.
- From December 2024 to the end of 2025, **10,109 employees** with PhDs in science, technology, engineering, math and health have left the federal workforce, taking decades of experience with them.

"The Unraveling of Public Science." Partnership for Public Service, 2026.

January 2026: <https://www.nature.com/immersive/d41586-026-00088-9/index.html>

January 2026: <https://www.nature.com/immersive/d41586-026-00088-9/index.html>

Impact on Science Data Collection and Distribution

- More than 3,000 data sets have been removed from public access.
- Part of the disruptions are created by workforce reductions; agencies have lost from 10-30% of their data staff.

"The Unraveling of Public Science." Partnership for Public Service, 2026.

2025: Grap and Run

marum

17

Data Rescue & Resilience

PANGAEA®
Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science

Impressions: 51,589
Reach: 26,815
Reactions: 999
Comments: 28

RESISTANCE WITH STORAGE SPACE Data recovery against Trump: How German researchers secure US environmental data

of Martin Scheufens 09. May 2025 - 16:42 - 5 min.

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7318581859896975360/>

NEWS | 24 April 2025 | Certification 28 April 2025

Major European institutes join race to save US science data

As the administration of US President Donald Trump slashes budgets, crucial data sets on climate and other subjects could disappear.

By Jeff Ingleton

<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-025-01309-3>

DIGITAL SOVEREIGNTY

Securing research data is "time-critical"

U.S. authorities will no longer provide much research data freely accessible in the future. Institutions in Germany are in the process of securing them.

From Charlotte Pardey / 15.05.2025

<https://www.forschung-und-lehre.de/forschung/sicherung-von-forschungsdaten-ist-zeitkritisch-7082>

NEWS | 03 April 2025 | Correction 09 April 2025

Massive budget cuts for US science proposed again by Trump administration

The 2027 budget proposal would curb federal payments for scientific publishing and reduce funding for many US institutions.

https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-026-01105-7?WT.ec_id=NATURE-202604

<https://www.gao.de/wissen/forschung-und-technik/kalenderlegung-gegen-trump--deutschis-forscher-reiten-us-umwelt-daten-35709114.html>

marum

18

18

Media Response

Grasp and Publish

National Geophysical Data Center / World Data Service (NGDC/WDS) (2025): Strong motion earthquake data values of digitized strong-motion accelerograms, 1933-1994 [dataset]. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.981245>

Always quote citation above when using data! You can download the citation in several formats below.
 Published: 2025-04-29 • DOI registered: 2025-06-12

National Geophysical Data Center / World Data Service (NGDC/WDS) (2025): Seismicity catalog collection, 2150 BC to 1996 AD [dataset]. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.981231>

Always quote citation above when using data! You can download the citation in several formats below.
 Published: 2025-04-29 • DOI registered: 2025-06-19

Data Rescue & Resilience: Mutual Aid Network of Repositories (MANR)

PANGAEA
Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science

WHEN DATA IS IN DANGER, I'M HERE TO RESCUE!

EQUIPPED FOR DATA RESCUE. PREPARED FOR ANY MISSION.

- 1 NETWORKS OF MUTUAL SUPPORT**
Building strong connections so no one (and no data) is left alone.
- 2 CREATION OF RESCUE-READY DATA PACKAGES**
Packaging data with metadata, documentation and checksums for quick and safe recovery.
- 3 STRESS-TESTING FRAMEWORK TO ASSESS VULNERABILITIES**
Testing systems under pressure to uncover weak points before disaster strikes.
- 4 CONTINGENCY LAYER**
An extra safety net of backups and alternate paths when plans change.
- 5 PRIORITISATION OF CRITICAL OR AT-RISK DATASETS**
Identifying what matters most so critical data gets the protection it needs first.

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AI generated based on a poster presented at EGU 2026 by Robert Huber, Uwe Schindler, Kerstin Lehnert, and Jens Klump

Thanks for your attention

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